

Spectro-analytical, X-ray diffraction and computational studies on *N'*-[(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]acetohydrazide and its copper complex

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Abstract : The structural properties of *N'*-[(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]acetohydrazide (NHMAH) have been investigated by various spectro-analytical techniques and computational studies. Energies, heat of formation, dipole moment values and Quantitative Structure Activity Relationships (QSAR) properties were computed employing ChemAxon and HyperChem 7.5 tools. The X-ray diffraction studies reveal the presence of both inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the crystal packing. The crystal system was found to be monoclinic, with $P2_1/c$ space group and the unit cell dimensions are : $a = 4.5025 \text{ \AA}$ (6), $b = 26.246 \text{ \AA}$ (3), $c = 8.3869 \text{ \AA}$ (14) and $Z = 4$. The pKa values are 10.9 and 13.2.

Dinuclear copper(II) complex of NHMAH is characterized by presence of mass peak at 481. The composition of the complex was also determined spectrophotometrically, by Job's method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method in DMF medium. Both the experiments confirmed 1 : 1 stoichiometry of the metal complex formed.

Keywords : *N'*-[(2-Hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]acetohydrazide (NHMAH), equilibrium studies, crystal structure, computational studies, spectrophotometric studies.

Introduction

Hydrazones are important class of compounds in medicinal fields. They are known to possess biological applications including anti-microbial, anti-convulsant, analgesic, anti-inflammatory and anti-tumorial activities. The acid hydrazides and their corresponding methyl hydrazides are of interest due to their remarkable biological activity. Studies revealed that the acetyl hydrazones can be used for protection against convulsions^{1,2}. The present study focuses on the structural properties of *N'*-[(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]acetohydrazide (NHMAH), by various spectro-analytical techniques viz. mass, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, DEPT and computational methods using ChemAxon and HyperChem 7.5 tools. Single crystal X-ray diffraction pattern and hydrogen bonding interactions of the NHMAH were also studied in the present investigation. This paper also deals with evaluation of binding properties of title compound with Cu^{II} using spectral, equilibrium and spectrophotometric studies.

Materials and methodology :

Synthesis of NHMAH : All the chemicals used were of Analytical Reagent (AR) grade. The title compound NHMAH was synthesised by two step procedure, (i) *preparation of acetohydrazide* : It was prepared following the literature methods³ and (ii) *preparation of NHMAH* : To a suspension of 0.0135 mol of acetohydrazide in 10 mL methanol, 0.0081 mol of salicylaldehyde was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with methanol, dried and recrystallized from methanol. The compound was separated out as a lemon yellow crystalline solid. The purity of the compound was checked by LC-MS and melting point.

Crystal growth : The recrystallized compound dissolved in DMF was allowed for slow evaporation by diffusion method in diethylether for crystal growth. Single crystals suitable for X-ray crystallographic analysis were obtained.

Synthesis of Cu^{II}-NHMAH : A solution of Cu^{II} metal

(0.0014 mol) was added to the hot methanolic solution of NHMAH (0.0028 mol) in 1 : 2 molar ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 10 h. The metal complex separated was filtered and washed with hot methanol, followed by washings with petroleum ether and finally dried. The resulting metal complex was characterized by mass, IR and elemental analyses. The stoichiometry of the complex was determined spectrophotometrically.

Physical measurements : Elemental analyses, IR, NMR and mass spectral studies were used for characterization. Mass spectral data were recorded on Shimadzu LCMS-2010A using atmospheric pressure chemical ionization in positive mode. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a JASCO FT/IR-5300 and the CHN elemental data were recorded on FLASH EA 1112 Series Thermofinnigan. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on ACF 200, Bruker, West Germany Super Conductivity Magnet. Spectrophotometric studies were carried on SL-171 Minispec spectrophotometer, where 1 cm cells were used. The equilibrium studies were carried out on a digital Digisun 707 pH-meter with an assembly of combined glass electrode maintaining the temperature constant. The dissociation constant of the ligand under study was calculated using Irving-Rossotti titration technique.

Computational studies : The computational studies were carried out by using Chemaxon and HyperChem 7.5 software. The energies of various conformers, heats of formation, energies, dipole moments, eigen values of HOMO and LUMO, QSAR properties are computed from these studies.

X-Ray crystallography : The single crystal X-ray diffraction data for NHMAH was collected on Bruker Smart APEX CCD diffractometer, area detector system equipped with a graphite monochromator and a Mo-K α fine-focus sealed tube ($\lambda(\text{Mo-K}\alpha) = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 298 K. A

Lindemann capillary was used for mounting the single crystal and 2400 frames were recorded with scanning angle ω of 0.3° , each for 5 s exposure with 0.5 mm collimated X-ray. The crystal and the detector were separated by distance of 60 mm for high resolution. The data collected was reduced by SAINTPLUS⁴; an empirical absorption correction was applied to the collected reflections with SADABS⁵, SHELXS-97⁶ was used for evaluating the structures and SHELXL-97⁷ was used for the refinement against F^2 . The generation of the crystal-packing diagram was done by mercury 1.4.1 of CCDC. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically and hydrogens were introduced on calculated positions and included in the refinement riding on their respective parent atoms.

Results and discussion

As the title compound has potential donor sites, an attempt is made to understand its bonding properties with Cu^{II} . The primary requisite to know about coordination sites is the use of equilibrium studies, which enable the determination of protonation and dissociation constants of the ligand. The interaction of metal ions with hydrazones is very interesting field as the variation in antimicrobial properties in ligand in presence of metal ions more often gives useful results in the field of pharmaceutical chemistry. The equilibrium studies by pH-metry and spectrophotometry methods gave information regarding pKa values of NHMAH and composition of its Cu^{II} complex respectively. As the thermodynamic energy parameters are important to compare experimental results with theoretical predictions, the required energy parameters were determined by computational methods. To understand structural properties of the acetyl hydrazine under study, the spectral data are recorded for pure ligand and its Cu^{II} complex (Table 1).

Table 1. Physical, analytical and mass spectral data of NHMAH and its Cu^{II} complex

Sl. no.	Ligand/Metal complex	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			Mass (m/z)	
			C	H	N	$[\text{M} + 1]^+$	$[\text{M} + \text{Na}]^+$
1.	NHMAH	Lemon yellow	58.71 (60.66)	5.10 (5.66)	14.55 (15.72)	179	201
2.	$[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-NMA}]_2$	Green	52.90 (55.86)	3.74 (4.78)	13.64 (14.61)	481	-

Spectral characterization of NHMAH :

Mass : The mass spectrum of NHMAH shows a dominant base peak at m/z 179, which is in accordance with the expected $[M+1]^+$ peak, analyzed under positive ionization conditions. This shows that the measured molecular mass is in good agreement with the theoretical value (178). The mass spectrum also shows a peak at m/z 201, which can be attributed to sodium adduct ions $[M+23]^+$.

IR : The band centered at 3186 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of NHMAH attributes to OH stretching vibrations and a strong band at 1682 cm^{-1} corresponds to carbonyl group of CONH. The aromatic and aliphatic ν_{C-H} vibrations are observed at 3070 and 2747, 2860 cm^{-1} respectively. A band at 1620 cm^{-1} corresponds to $\nu_{C=N}$ vibrations. Peaks at 1437 and 1388 cm^{-1} are characteristic to the methyl group and a strong band at 756 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of *ortho*-disubstituted aromatic ring.

NMR : The ^1H NMR spectrum of NHMAH in $\text{CDCl}_3 + \text{DMSO-}d_6$ mixture recorded signals at δ 1.91, 2.1 (d, CH_3), 6.69–8.10 (m, aromatic CH), 8.57 (s, azomethine). The split in the CH_3 signal and presence of more number of signals than expected indicates that NHMAH may be present in different conformers. The ^{13}C NMR spectral data showed a complex spectrum with more number of peaks than expected indicating the existence of the compound in different conformational isomers. The OH and NH peaks are identified by their ready exchange with water. The DEPT 45 and 135 recorded CH and CH_3 signals and DEPT 90 recorded CH signals. These spectra also showed the presence of more number of signals than expected indicating the existence of conformational isomerism in NHMAH.

The analysis of NMR spectrum revealed existence of two forms. Hence there is a possibility for the existence of two conformers associated with relatively low energies in solution, even though there are many conformational forms from the computational studies in gaseous state of the molecule. Further, the existence of keto-enol tautomerism cannot be ruled out. The possible conformers of NHMAH were computed from Chemaxon⁸ programme. The energies of various conformers range from 27.7 kcal/mol to 34.04 kcal/mol. Hence, the structures of the high-

est and lowest energy conformers of keto and enol forms of NHMAH are given (Figs. 1a and 1b) and the energies of the other conformers are tabulated (Table 2).

Table 2. Energies of various conformers of keto and enol forms of NHMAH

Keto form		Enol form	
Conformer	Energy (kcal/mol)	Conformer	Energy (kcal/mol)
1	27.7	1	31.55
2	28.49	2	31.59
3	28.72	3	31.59
4	28.96	4	31.61
5	29.15	5	31.66
6	29.48	6	31.67
7	29.64	7	33.87
8	29.67	8	33.90
9	30.21	9	34.04
10	30.27	10	34.04

Conf: 1 Energy: 27.7 kcal/mol Conf: 10 Energy: 30.27 kcal/mol

Fig. 1(a). Highest and lowest conformers of keto form.

Conf: 1 Energy: 31.55 kcal/mol Conf: 10 Energy: 34.04 kcal/mol

Fig. 1(b). Highest and lowest conformers of enol form.

X-Ray crystallographic studies :

N'-[(2-Hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]acetohydrazide (NHMAH) is a molecule having nine carbon atoms, ten hydrogen atoms, two nitrogen atoms and two oxygen atoms. A perspective ORTEP⁹ view of the molecule NHMAH ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$) with the labelling and numbering of non-hydrogen atoms is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. X-Ray crystal structure of NHMAH with 50% probability for non-H atoms.

The unit cell parameters, experimental details and refinement parameters are listed in Table 3. The crystal system is monoclinic with $P2_1/c$ space group. The structure reveals presence of four molecules of NHMAH per unit cell ($Z = 4$).

Table 3. Single crystal X-ray diffraction data and structure refinement for N' -[(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]acetohydrazide at 298 K

CCDC	812185
Empirical formula	$C_9H_{10}N_2O_2$
Formula weight	178.19
Temperature	293(2) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 4.5025(6)$ Å $b = 26.246(3)$ Å $c = 8.3869(14)$ Å $\beta = 116.799(12)^\circ$
Volume	$884.7(2)$ Å ³
Z	4
Density (calculated)	1.338 mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	0.097 mm ⁻¹
$F(000)$	376
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.42 × 0.32 × 0.10
Theta range for data collection	2.83 to 26.37°
Index ranges	$-5 < = h < = 4$, $-32 < = k < = 20$, $-8 < = l < = 10$
Reflections collected	3701
Independent reflections	1818 [$R(\text{int}) = 0.0338$]
Completeness to theta = 26.37°	99.9%
Max. and min. transmission	0.9904 and 0.9605
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	1818/0/119
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.020
Final R indices [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R1 = 0.0616$, $wR2 = 0.1168$
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.1154$, $wR2 = 0.1412$
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.214 and -0.191 e.Å ⁻³

The bond lengths and bond angles data is given in Table 4 and Table 5 respectively. A comparison of the bond lengths and bond angles obtained from the crystal structure and the computed values from the molecular model built, reveals a good agreement of these values. The hydrogen bonding interactions indicate that NHMAH has three hydrogen bond donors and two hydrogen bond acceptors. All the hydrogen atoms were located from difference Fourier maps. Further, the analysis of hydrogen bonding showed the presence of three types of hydrogen bonds: $O-H \cdots N$, $N-H \cdots O$ and $C-H \cdots O$. Both inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonding is observed in the crystal packing, $O(1)-H(1) \cdots N(1)$ is intramolecular while $N(2)-H(2A) \cdots O(2)$ and $C(9)-H(9A) \cdots O(2)$ are intermolecular (Fig. 3).

Table 4. Comparison of the bond lengths [Å] – experimental data from XRD and computed data from HyperChem 7.5

	X-Ray diffraction studies	Semi-empirical PM3
C(6)-O(1)	1.365 (3)	1.369
C(7)-N(1)	1.285 (3)	1.303
C(8)-O(2)	1.234 (3)	1.387
C(8)-N(2)	1.350 (3)	1.216
C(8)-C(9)	1.490 (4)	1.430
N(1)-N(2)	1.379 (2)	1.509

Table 5. Bond angles [°] for N' -[(2-hydroxyphenyl)methylidene]acetohydrazide

	X-Ray diffraction studies	Semi-empirical PM3
O(1)-C(6)-C(5)	117.3(2)	117.7
O(1)-C(6)-C(1)	122.6(2)	121.4
N(1)-C(7)-C(1)	121.0(2)	120.1
O(2)-C(8)-N(2)	119.0(2)	120.8
O(2)-C(8)-C(9)	122.7(2)	124.4
C(7)-N(1)-N(2)	116.6(2)	120.6

Fig. 3. A view of the molecular arrangement and intermolecular interactions of NHMAH in solid state.

Careful analysis reveals that, in solid state structure, the molecules are held together by N(2)—H(2A)····O(2) #1 and C(9)—H(9A)····O(2) #2 hydrogen bonding interactions wherein, each molecule is interlinked to two different molecules with H(2A)····O(2) and H(9A)····O(2) bond distances of 1.92 and 2.53 Å respectively. The bond strengths in the intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions is in the order : N—H····O > C—H····O. The zero restraints indicate the absence of dihedral angle.

Computational studies :

The molecule was built using the HyperChem 7.5 software¹⁰. The geometry optimization was carried out using the semi-empirical method at Parametric Method 3 (PM3) level. Table 6 shows the values computed for the energy, dipole moment, heat of formation and energies of HOMO and LUMO. Energy properties were calculated using PM3 method (Table 7a).

The electron density surfaces of highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and lowest unoccupied mo-

drazone group is certainly suitable for the coordination with metal ions. The energies and eigen values of HOMO in both keto and enol forms are comparable, but there is variation in dipole moments and eigen values of LUMO orbitals. The negative eigen values which correspond to vertical ionization values of electrons indicate that the LUMO orbitals are more bonding type in enol form.

Quantitative structure activity relationship studies (QSAR studies) :

The main success of the QSAR method is the possibility to estimate the characteristics of new chemical compounds. QSAR properties like surface area, volume, hydration energy, log *P*, refractivity, polarisability of NHMAH were determined by single point PM3 method (Table 7b).

Equilibrium studies :

The potentiometric titrations were carried out in 70% DMF-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. The proton-ligand constants (pKa) of the ligand

Table 6. Data of molecular and orbital properties

Compd.	Energy (kcal/mol)	Dipole moment (debye)	Heat of formation (kcal/mol)	Molecular orbitals (eV)	
				HOMO (MO : 34)	LUMO (MO : 35)
Keto form	-49142.4924	4.36618	-23.40	-8.647592	-0.3044452
Enol form	-49139.42519	1.02107	-20.33	-8.686239	-0.3317081

Table 7. Energy parameters and QSAR properties of NHMAH obtained by semi-empirical PM3 geometry calculations

(a) Energy parameters :

Total energy	-49142.49219 kcal/mol
Binding energy	-2427.54782 kcal/mol
Nuclear energy	207517.4219 kcal/mol
Electronic energy	-256659.9219 kcal/mol

(b) QSAR properties :

Surface area	354.46 Å ²
Volume	582.31 Å ³
Hydration energy	-10.90 kcal/mol
Refractivity	49.27 Å ³
Polarizability	18.95 Å ³
log <i>P</i>	1.23

lecular orbital (LUMO) of the keto (Fig. 4) and enol (Fig. 5) forms generated from the calculations for the neutral ground states of the molecules are displayed. The orientation of HOMO and LUMO orbitals at carboxy hy-

have been evaluated by analyzing these pH titration curves using Irving-Rossotti technique¹¹. These studies revealed that the title compound has two dissociable protons - 10.9 and 13.2 (Fig. 6).

The lower pKa value corresponds to dissociation of hydroxyl group present on phenyl group and the higher pKa represent the NH proton dissociation in carboxy hydrazone moiety of NHMAH. The NH proton dissociation either takes place from nitrogen itself or from oxygen via enol form. But earlier studies¹² have supported that dissociation via enol form through oxygen is easier as the proton acquires relatively more acidic character in enol form compared to keto form.

Spectral characterization of the [Cu(NMA)]₂ :

Mass : The mass spectrum of NHMAH shows a dominant base peak at *m/z* 179, which is in accordance with

Keto-HOMO

Keto-LUMO

Fig. 4. HOMO and LUMO of keto form of NHMAH.

Enol-HOMO

Enol-LUMO

Fig. 5. HOMO and LUMO of enol form of NHMAH.

the expected $[M + 1]^+$ peak, analyzed under positive ionization conditions. This shows that the measured molecular mass is in good agreement with the theoretical value (178). The mass spectrum of copper(II) complex exhibited a base peak at m/z 241 and a low abundance peak at m/z 481.

Fig. 6. pH titration curve of NHMAH in 70% DMF-water medium at 303 K and 0.1 M KNO_3 .

The m/z 481 corresponds to $[M + 1]^+$ peak of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NMA})]_2$ composition. While the base peak at 241 indicates $[M + 1]^+$ of monomer fragment $[\text{Cu}(\text{NMA})]$. The mass spectral data thus indicates the 1 : 1 stoichiometry of Cu^{II} complex.

IR : The IR spectrum of NHMAH recorded $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ peaks at 1682 and 1620 cm^{-1} . The corresponding peaks exhibited a shift in Cu^{II} complex. The observed peaks at 1622, 1604, 1541, 1512 cm^{-1} are attributable to the formation of conjugated diimine ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{C}-$) and thus indicate participation of carbonyl 'O' and imine 'N' through dissociation of proton¹³. This observation infers the formation of enol form of ligand prior to its coordination with metal ion. The proton dissociation thus takes place from enol form while forming bond with metal ion. The IR spectrum of the ligand also showed the peaks at 3186, 3070, 2947, 2860 cm^{-1} corresponding to N-H, O-H and C-H vibrations. In the IR spectrum of the metal complex, the weak absorptions at 3022–2922 cm^{-1} indicate C-H stretching frequencies of aliphatic, aromatic and azomethine groups. As there are no absorptions for N-H and O-H vibrations in the spectrum of the complex, the loss of phenolic and amide protons is confirmed. The dimeric nature of Cu^{II} complexes is further confirmed by the appearance of $\text{M} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \diagdown \text{O} \diagup \end{array} \text{M}$ ring vibration at 729 cm^{-1} ¹⁴.

Determination of the composition of the metal complex :

An attempt is made to establish the stoichiometric metal to ligand ratio of the complex formed from Cu^{II} and NHMAH spectrophotometrically by using Job's method and mole-ratio method.

Job's continuous variation method :

In this method, the solutions of Cu^{II} and NHMAH with identical concentrations (0.001 M) are mixed in different volume ratios, keeping total volume of the mixture constant (25 mL)¹⁵. The pH of the solutions was maintained at 6.04 by addition of sodium acetate buffer. The absorbance of each solution was measured at a wavelength 605 nm (λ_{max}). A graph was plotted between the absorbance (Y-axis) and mole-fraction of the ligand (X-axis). The graph showed a maximum absorbance value at 0.5 mole fraction of the ligand, which corresponds to 1 : 1 stoichiometric metal to ligand ratio.

Mole-ratio method :

A series of solutions are prepared such that, the molar concentration of the metal ion is held constant and that of the ligand i.e. NHMAH is varied¹⁵. The pH of the solutions is maintained at 6.04 by sodium acetate buffer. A graph is plotted between absorbance and the volume of the ligand. Two straight lines of different slopes are obtained; the intersection of the two lines occurs at a mole ratio corresponding to their combination in the complex.

Conclusions :

The ligand NHMAH and its copper complex have been synthesized and characterized by spectro-analytical techniques. X-Ray crystallographic study determines its structure. The NMR studies indicate that NHMAH exhibits conformational isomerism. The small differences in energies of different conformers are evident from computational studies. The equilibrium studies reveal that the ligand is a dibasic acid. The electron density figures of HOMO and LUMO of NHMAH support the suitability of molecular orbitals oriented along carboxy hydrazone moiety for bonding with metal ion.

The formation of dinuclear copper(II) complex with 1 : 1 (M : L) stoichiometry is evident from mass spectral data. From the above studies, the tentative structure for dinuclear Cu^{II} complex of NHMAH is assigned showing one of the oxygen as bridging donor (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Tentative structure of [Cu^{II}-(NMA)]₂ complex.

Supplementary information

Crystallographic data (including structure factors) for the structure reported in this paper has been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre as supplementary publication no. CCDC 812185.

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